

DENSITY DEPENDENT MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF GLASSFIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES MADE OF NON-WOVEN FABRICS

Sebastian Iwan, Matthias Klaerner and Lothar Kroll

Institute of Lightweight Structures, Technische Universität Chemnitz
09107 Chemnitz, Germany

Email: sebastian.iwan@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <http://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de>

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ABSTRACT

Glassfibre-reinforced thermoplastics based on non-woven fabrics (Figure 1) are an important material for the mass production of composite parts. The semi-finished mats are characterised by randomly oriented matrix and reinforcement fibre bundles. Thus, the material properties are assumed to be isotropic but in detail show a low degree of anisotropy due to the manufacturing direction in line production.

The non-woven fabrics are consolidated using a two-staged thermal pressing process. First, the mat is heated above the melting point of the matrix fibres e.g. in an electric contact heater. Next, the preheated mat is placed in a tempered mould for consolidation and cooling. The variation of the press-stroke with different separators in the mould allows to adjust the compression of the mats with a constant surface weight and though to control the density. For comparison to past and future results the degree of consolidation is introduced in addition, which can be used to describe the relationship between surface weight, density, fibre volume content and thickness of the mats.

Due to the different compression levels, the material properties tend to be dependent on the density. Thus, the static and dynamic properties have been analysed using a mat with a constant area weight of 1250 g/m², a fibre mass content of 25 %, 40 % and 55 %, machine and cross direction as well as five different densities. The results of this study show the potential of influencing the stiffness and strength by adjusting the consolidation of glassfibre-reinforced composites made of non-woven fabrics. In contrast, the damping properties are not sensitive to the density.

Figure 1: Non-woven fabrics and consolidated plates

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

The mechanical properties like tensile modulus, tensile strength and impact strength of natural fibre-reinforced plastics (NFRP) are highly dependent on the component thickness [Baur09A]. The described NFRP consist of a thermoset or thermoplastic matrix (e.g. Lignoflex) and have a constant surface weight. Their mechanical properties can be regulated by varying the level of consolidation of the semi-finished fabrics and with that the composite density [Baur09B, Rinb12]. In order to use the density-dependent NFRP-material properties in praxis, construction instructions have already been released for the optimal design of pressed NFRP-components that consist of flax fibre and a polyurethane matrix [Rinb2012]. Thus, the aim is realising a high level of lightweight design by using different densities in areas with requirements on material stiffness and strength. Composite areas that are exposed to bending stress will be realised with lower material density in order to achieve a higher bending stiffness. This is caused by an over-proportionally increasing moment of inertia and an almost linear reduced tensile modulus at the same time. Areas with high requirements on material strength, like high load introduction areas, have to be realised with high densities in order to achieve a sufficiently high load-bearing capacity of the material.

There are no evaluations documented in literature that investigate the material properties of glassfibre-reinforced plastics that are based on a non-woven material with PP matrix. Moreover, there is no evaluation method enabling the investigation of damping features against different composite thickness.

2 MATERIAL SELECTION AND MANUFACTURING

Glass mat thermoplastics (GMT) are increasingly coming into use for interior and exterior cladding components in vehicles. The materials are chosen according to the application's requirements and are existent in a large variety of fibre or matrix material as well as versatile fibre mass content in the form of textile semi-finished mats or consolidated preforms.

The investigated material is a glassfibre-reinforced thermoplastic based on a needled non-woven semi-finished fabric. The GMT has been manufactured with three different fibre mass contents (FMF=25 %, 40 % and 55 %) and a constant surface weight of 1250 g/m². Both, the fibre alignment on the carding machine as well as the subsequent cross-directional orientation of the pile within the manufacturing process cause anisotropic properties. Therefore, only the machine direction (MD) and the cross direction (CD) will be examined within the following investigation. The design of experiments is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variations within the parametric study of non-woven fabrics

The non-woven fabric plates were consolidated using a two-staged thermal pressing process. First, the mat was heated above the melting point of the matrix fibres in an electric contact heater. Next, the preheated mat was placed in a 100°C lower tempered mould for consolidation and cooling. In order to achieve plates in different densities, spacers were used to regulate the plate thickness within the manufacturing process. The desired plate thickness of different levels of consolidation has been determined on the basis of lowest possible plate thickness at highest consolidation level. Figure 3 shows the relationship between the thickness of the semi-finished textile fabric and the corresponding desired thicknesses, densities and consolidation levels.

Figure 3: Desired thickness, density and level of consolidation of GMT

The desired thickness t_{des} of the partially consolidated plates

$$t_{des} = \frac{t_{min}}{C} \quad (1)$$

is determined by the consolidation level C and the plate thickness t_{min} of a totally consolidated fibre-plastic-composite

$$t_{min} = \frac{\Gamma}{\varphi_v \cdot \rho_f + (1 - \varphi_v) \cdot \rho_m} \quad (2)$$

on the basis of the surface weight Γ , the fibre volume contents φ_v and the density ρ of the matrix (m) and fibre material (f): Figure 4.

Figure 4: Thickness of partially and fully consolidated plates

Figure 5 shows magnifications of plates with different levels of consolidation in a range of 0.6 (left) to 1.0 (right) for 1000 g/m² and a fibre mass fraction of 55 % exemplarily. The decreasing amount of air inclusions is clearly visible. Nevertheless, plates with less consolidation show worthwhile compression stiffness and strength in normal directions.

Figure 5: Magnification (100x) of plates with different levels of consolidation

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In measuring the elastic modulus as well as tensile strength, the mechanical properties of the GMT have been determined according to the DIN EN ISO 527-4 by using flat samples. The experiments were carried out at quasi-static testing speed and at room temperature.

In order to investigate the damping behaviour at bending stress cantilever beams were subjected to vibration experiments (see Figure 6 [Klae2015]). The sample is held by a defined pre-tension and is set into horizontal oscillations by inductive excitation and a so called anchor weight which is applied on the sample. The excitation was carried out in the cantilever beam's first natural bending frequency. After cutting off the coil voltage, the v-t-curves of the reverberation were tracked without direct contact by a Laser-Doppler-vibrometer.

Figure 6: Experimental setup for the determination of the vibration damping: 1) Laser-Doppler-vibrometer, 2) inductive excitation, 3) cantilever beam specimen, 4) clamping and force monitoring

Viscous damping has been reasonably assumed for the dynamic behaviour. Thus, the damping ratio can be determined on the basis of the oscillation decay curve (velocity over time and envelope function) and the damping coefficient δ .

$$v(t) = A \cdot e^{-\delta t} \cdot \cos(\omega t - \alpha) \quad (3)$$

$$v_E(t) = \pm A \cdot e^{-\delta t} \quad (4)$$

Moreover, the component's first natural frequency ω_1 has to be taken into consideration to

determine the damping ratio.

$$D = \frac{\delta}{\omega_1} \quad (5)$$

Figure 7 shows an example of a decay curve. The exponential attenuation behaviour shows the agreement of both the decay curve and the envelope function. This viscous damping behaviour could be recorded for all cantilever beam samples. Furthermore, it is apparent that the samples only swing in their first natural frequency.

Figure 7: Decay curve of a cantilever beam: velocity over time and envelope function

4 RESULTS

The static and mechanical properties have been summarised to means according to the test series and have been compared in terms of the gathered actual plate densities. The actual plate densities had been calculated from the sample dimensions and sample weights.

Due to the fibre alignment on the carding machine and the pile's subsequent cross-directional orientation within the manufacturing process better mechanical properties are to be expected in CD-direction than in MD-direction. Figure 8 demonstrates the dependency of the tensile modulus on different fibre orientations. Furthermore, it can be seen that the tensile modulus ascends with increasing material density and increasing fibre mass fraction. The tensile modulus is equally dependent on density, fibre orientation and fibre mass fraction for which reason a lot of material properties can be regulated according to the requirements during the manufacturing process.

Figure 8: Tensile modulus over density with different orientations and fibre mass fractions

The increase in density usually results in higher tensile strength, too (see Figure 9). While the dependency of the tensile modulus on the material density can clearly be seen in CD-direction for low fibre mass fractions, the curve shapes of the tensile modulus are quite similar for the different fibre mass fractions in MD-direction.

Figure 9: Tensile strength over density with different orientations and fibre mass fractions

During the component design the effects that may result from different inertia moments have to be taken into consideration for thin-walled components that are exposed to bending stress. Therefore, a fractional sample-width has been determined from the tensile modulus and the sample thickness. All samples show a lower bending stiffness with increasing density (see Figure 10). The curve gradients vary for different FMF and fibre orientations.

Figure 10: Bending stiffness related to beam width over density with different orientations and fibre mass fractions

Figure 11 shows the influence of the different plate thicknesses on both the bending stiffness and tensile modulus. The determined value range helps to identify the optimal FMF and orientation for combined bending-traction material stress. The corresponding desired plate thicknesses can be seen in Figure 8 and Figure 10.

Figure 11: Bending stiffness related to beam width over young's modulus with different orientations, fibre mass fractions and thus different densities

As shown in Figure 12, an increase in density has no significant influence on the damping properties of the GMT-material. The matrix material clearly dominates the frp damping properties. Accordingly, the reduction of the fibre mass fraction or the MD-alignment causes higher damping.

Figure 12: Damping ratio over density with different orientations and fibre mass fractions

With regard to the tensile modulus of the examined samples, Figure 13 shows the antithetical damping and stiffness behaviour. The damping properties decrease with an increasing tensile modulus. Within a specific fibre mass fraction or fibre orientation a comparatively high tensile modulus with almost constant damping properties can be reached through a high material density. Samples in MD-direction tend to have a slightly higher damping ratio.

Figure 13: Damping ratio over young's modulus with different orientations and fibre mass fractions

9 CONCLUSIONS

Fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites based on non-woven fabrics offer a wide range for the modification of elastic and dynamic material properties. In addition to the variation of the fibre mass fraction and the fibre orientation material properties, like material stiffness and material strength, can be varied by using different levels of consolidation and thus material densities. The material properties show an almost mutual linear dependency and are well reproducible.

In general, fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites show an antithetical damping and stiffness behaviour, although the damping properties are better than those of metal or fibre-reinforced thermoset composites.

The presented density dependent static material properties of non-woven fabrics are already used for enhancing the lightweight potential of car interior components.

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